

ADS DATA MODEL

Work package	WP1 Market Data Analysis
Task	T1.1 ADS data model development based on existing data
Due date	30/06/2025
Submission date	30/06/2025
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Version	1.0
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DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description	List of Contributors
0.1	09/06/2025	First version: ADS Data Model purpose, methodology and initial insights (dashboard).	Anu Passi-Rauste, Ivana Pesic, Andres Felipe Zapata Palacio, Harri Ketamo (Headai)
0.2	13/06/2025	Comments and additions by the reviewer	Brendan Rowan (BLU)
0.3	25/06/2025	Updates on following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the sample – geographical coverage, spread of roles or companies, number of skills present. • Description of how the results are interpreted/extrapolated from the sample to EU level. • Table of results per tech area and per skills pockets (as annex) • A map of the evolution of the model from V1.0 to what will come in V2.0 and V3.0. 	Anu Passi-Rauste, Ivana Pesic, Andres Felipe Zapata Palacio, Harri Ketamo (Headai)
0.4	26/06/2025	References across sections to relevant reports, initiatives, etc. added	Cristian Salis (BLU)
1.0	27/05/2025	References added.	Anu Passi-Rauste, Harri Ketamo (Headai)

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DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc
DMP: Data management plan
ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.
SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ADS	Advanced Digital Skills
ADSEU	Advanced Digital Skills Europe Platform
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CTF	Communications Task Force
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DIGITAL	Digital Europe Programme
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
SO4	Strategic Objective 4 of the Digital Europe Programme

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ADS Data Model forms the analytical core of LEADSx2030's Market Data Analysis, enabling data-based foresight and decision-making for Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) development across Europe. The ADS Data Model (v1.0) aggregates structured and unstructured data from labour market, research, and investment sources, harmonising them through a semantic AI framework that enables real-time and predictive insights. At the center of the model are skills pockets, semantically clustered groups of related ADS that allow for consistent cross-sector analysis, benchmarking, and demand forecasting.

The model is designed to overcome long-standing fragmentation in skills intelligence, moving beyond static taxonomies and enabling dynamic tracking of skills evolution. Using methods such as language model-driven NLP, graph-based clustering, and digital twin generation, the model interprets skills demand and signals from over 4 million EU job ads, 10 million open-access research articles, and 100,000 investment records. This diverse dataset fuels scenario-building and demand prediction at both macro and micro levels.

The outputs are integrated into a public dashboard (<https://advancedskills.eu/ads-demand-dashboard-2025/>) and made available to stakeholders also as JSON/CSV data, enabling diverse use cases. These include skills forecasting, curriculum design support, supply-demand matching, and gap analysis.

The ADS Data Model and especially its data sources will continue to evolve during the project. Upcoming iterations (v2.0 and v3.0) will place greater emphasis on education and training data. The primary source for these additions will be contributions made via the LEADSx2030 Data Hub, facilitated by the data space approach. This development trajectory ensures sustained analytical relevance through 2030.

The model is designed to support all LEADSx2030 activities by underpinning the benchmarking and coordination of ADS offering under the SO4 ADS Cluster, and strategic recommendations. By enabling semantic interoperability and generating actionable insights from diverse data sources, the ADS Data Model provides a robust foundation for aligning European education, policy, and industry initiatives with the continent's rapidly evolving digital skills landscape.

1 Introduction

1.1 About LEADSx2030

LEADSx2030 is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded under the Advanced Digital Skills Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) of the DIGITAL Programme. As a CSA, it is tasked with:

- Delivering insights into the changing advanced digital skills demands in the EU, and determining to what extent the current education and training offers match the needs of the current and future labour market.
- Recommending priority areas for new funding programmes and giving indications on which type of programmes and training is most effective for building up advanced digital skills.
- Supporting excellence in education and training institutions, aiming at the development of a dynamic digital education and training ecosystem.
- Promoting collaboration among the SO4 Cluster, i.e. the consortia awarded from the different call topics under the DIGITAL SO4.

As such, over a period of 48 months LEADSx2030 will:

- Provide a continuous review of demand and supply changes related to advanced digital skills.
- Map the outputs of the SO4 Cluster to identify key results and success stories.
- Develop the SO4 Cluster into a dynamic network.
- Provide opportunities for synergies with relevant European actors.
- Bring all stakeholders together in point-of-reference annual advanced digital skills summits.
- Support the strategic EU policy objectives through targeted analyses and recommendations.

Latest information about the initiative can be found at www.advancedskills.eu.

1.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for Data Model

A key activity in the LEADSx2030 project is developing the analytical foundation for understanding and anticipating changes in Europe's Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) landscape. For the market data analysis LEADSx2030 is:

- Developing the ADS Data Model → AI-driven framework, based on known big data sets, for analysing workforce skills demand.
- Establishing Data Hub Connection → The technical integration of the ADS Data Hub into the EU workforce analytics ecosystem.

Annual updates are arranged to ensure continuous improvement of workforce intelligence models.

The AI-driven ADS Data Model is designed to:

- Aggregate data from multiple sources (education, labour markets, research etc.).
- Harmonise terminology and structures across datasets through semantic modelling, i.e. semantic interoperability.
- Generate structured, data-based insights into the evolving requirements for ADS.
- Provide dynamic analytics and insights to support workforce development.

The ADS Data Model is being developed using a wide range of existing and emerging data related to skills demand and supply, such as job advertisements, education and training programme descriptions, research publications, and investment reports. Through semantic integration and

alignment of these data sources, the model is enabling both real-time mapping of current trends and predictive foresight into future skills needs.

The ADS Data Model and advanced AI methods are being applied for semantic clustering, skills matching, and trend forecasting. The outputs of the model are disseminated via an interactive dashboard that supports transparency and usability for a wide range of stakeholders.

Importantly, the ADS Data Model serves as the core intelligence layer powering a continuously updated view of the skills ecosystem. By operating through an open and integrated hub structure, the model enables a continuous review of demand and supply changes in ADS across Europe. Rather than a static taxonomy, the model reflects the dynamic evolution of skills signals and adjusts as new skills emerge from the labour markets.

Expected outcomes for the functioning ADS Data Model:

- Enable semantic interoperability, measurability and comparability between different data sources.
- Provides data-based insights into the changing requirements for ADS.
- Maps skills demand and supply using multiple structured and unstructured data sources.
- Matches and forecasts skill needs by tech areas.

This model is acting as the analytical core of the LEADSx2030 project, enabling recommendation-building, benchmarking, and real-time monitoring across the ADS landscape.

1.3 Scope of this deliverable

This deliverable outlines the work carried out to develop the ADS Data Model, designed to support data- and evidence-based understanding of Europe's ADS landscape.

The purpose of this document is to describe how the model is being used to produce data-based insights into the changing requirements for advanced digital skills, by mapping demand and supply from different data sources and matching these across e.g. tech areas.

A central focus of the work has been the definition and refinement of skills pockets, semantically clustered groupings of ADS that enable structured comparison across heterogeneous datasets. The report presents how these skills pockets have been constructed, maintained, and used as the analytical foundation for matching and forecasting skill needs.

This deliverable also provides an overview of the rationale, structure, and components of the ADS Data Model, including its core methods, source integration, and intended use cases.

2 Purpose for ADS Data Model and identified use cases

2.1 Purpose for the ADS Data Model

The ADS Data Model was designed to address a critical fragmentation in skills intelligence across Europe. Skills-related information is spread across multiple domains – job advertisements, curriculums, patents, investment strategies, research publications – each written in different terminologies, formats, and for different audiences. This heterogeneity creates barriers to effective comparison, analysis, and strategic planning.

The core aim of the ADS Data Model is to introduce semantic interoperability among these diverse datasets. Rather than enforcing a top-down taxonomy, the model constructs a dynamic, AI-driven semantic structure that maps various expressions of digital skills into shared conceptual representations. For example, terms like “IT security,” “cybersecurity,” and “data protection” are aligned into common, understandable clusters through similarity analysis using language models.

The model enables structured matching and analysis across:

- Demand-side data (e.g., job ads, investments, research).
- Supply-side data (e.g., training program descriptions, curricula).

These inputs are harmonised into “skills pockets”: semantically grouped clusters of related digital skills that act as the core analytical units of the model. This enables deep analysis of:

- Foundation skills, skills that are needed in the past present and future.
- Skills emergence and obsolescence.
- Gaps between supply and demand.
- Signals and anomalies.
- Sector-specific and technology-specific demand trends.
- Foresight into evolving labour market needs.

By delivering consistent, structured, and explainable insights from heterogeneous data, the ADS Data Model creates the foundation for evidence-based strategic decisions in workforce planning, funding, education design, and policymaking.

2.2 Policy makers use case

For policy makers, the ADS Data Model offers critical intelligence to support strategic decision-making on digital skills development across Europe. By aggregating and harmonising data from job advertisements, training programmes, and innovation data like research and investments the model provides a consolidated evidence base to:

- Identify supply–demand mismatches: Pinpoint specific domains where the supply of ADS falls short of current or projected labour market demand.
- Plan funding programmes and education reforms: Use data-backed insights to design and target new funding schemes, curriculum updates, or capacity-building measures for training providers.

- Detect early warning signals on emerging skill gaps: Track technological shifts and new demand patterns before they escalate into structural workforce shortages, enabling anticipatory responses at national and EU levels.

The model enables policy makers to move from fragmented, lagging data to a proactive, foresight-driven approach — improving alignment between labour market realities and education, funding, and policy planning at national and European levels.

2.3 Training providers use case

The model empowers educational institutions to enhance their offerings and remain relevant:

- Benchmark offerings: Compare existing curriculum and training programs against real-time demand indicators.
- Understand skills trends: Gain deep insights into evolving skills trends within their specific sectors.
- Adjust curriculum and develop new programmes: Adapt existing courses and design innovative training programs that directly address identified market needs.

By leveraging the outputs of the ADS Data Model, training providers can shift from reactive course development to a proactive, demand-driven approach, ensuring their learners acquire the most relevant and future-proof skills.

2.4 LEADSx2030 Partners use case

The outputs of the ADS Data Model are integral to other activities in the remit of LEADSx2030:

- ADS Longitudinal Analysis: Utilises model outputs to benchmark the coverage and effectiveness of existing training programmes under the SO4 ADS Cluster.
- SO4 ADS Cluster Coordination: Identifies successful approaches and best practices from the SO4 Cluster based on the model's insights.
- Recommendations and Reporting: Leverages the Data Model to generate data-backed policy briefs and comprehensive "State-of-Play" reports.

3 Methodology, ADS Data Model and Data Hub

3.1 Concept, Architecture, Skills pockets, AI Analysis

This chapter details the foundational methodology underpinning the ADS Data Model, encompassing its conceptual framework and architecture, skills pockets, AI analysis methods and forecasting capabilities.

3.1.1 Concept

The concept of the ADS Data Model originates from a foundational challenge: skills-related data is typically unstructured, created for varying purposes, and highly context-specific. Job postings, education programme descriptions, investment portfolios, and scientific research all include skill-relevant content, but they use different terms, formats, and classifications. This fragmentation makes it difficult to compare or synthesise the data directly.

The Data Model addresses this challenge by establishing semantic interoperability across these heterogeneous sources. It does not rely on a fixed taxonomy; instead, it creates a shared conceptual framework that maps varied terms onto common semantic spaces. Skills are mapped based on Headai focused language model, which is semantically aligned with widely recognised ontologies and frameworks such as ESCO¹, ISCO², SOC³, and O*NET⁴.

The core idea is not to produce a static database, but rather a dynamic, structured representation of skills that reflects real-time developments. This enables Europe to move from fragmented signals to cohesive, actionable insights. The model provides a foundation for meaningful tracking, benchmarking, and forecasting of digital skills across sectors, geographies, and institutional boundaries.

Outputs from the model are provided in JSON format and as CSV for further analysis and visualisation.

3.1.2 Data Model Framework and Architecture

The framework consists of several layers:

- Technology area: Groupings aligned with digital transformation domains (e.g., AI, IoT, cybersecurity).
- Skill pockets: Clusters / groups of neighbouring digital skills, needed together in real world.
- Digital skills: The atomic units observed in data, the skill in the context of LEADSx2030 can be a tool, technology, method, piece knowledge, etc. or a skill as defined in academic studies.

¹ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

² <https://ilostat.ilo.org/methods/concepts-and-definitions/classification-occupation/>

³ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/classificationsandstandards/standardoccupationalclassificationsoc/soc2020>

⁴ <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/eta/onet>

This structure enables analysis at multiple levels, allowing users to examine broad sectoral trends or zoom in to specific competencies. The architecture also supports longitudinal tracking, as each skills pocket is versioned and monitored over time.

Table 1. Example breakdown that describes the framework used for the Data Model

Technology Area	Skill Pocket	Example Skills
Artificial Intelligence	Machine Learning Engineering	Neural Networks, Model Optimisation
IoT	Industrial Automation	SCADA Systems, Edge Computing
Cybersecurity	Healthcare Data Security	HIPAA Compliance, Encryption

Breakdown of the analytical structure

All the numerical analyses over ADS will have a specific level of granularity, allowing analyses divided by technological area.

The areas that will be covered include:

- Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- Autonomous Systems.
- Blockchain.
- Cloud Computing.
- Cybersecurity.
- Data Science.
- Digital Twin.
- Edge Computing.
- Internet of Things (IoT).
- Robotics.

Each technological area is composed of multiple skills pockets. One skill pocket can belong to 1 or more areas, but its value will be calculated independently for each area.

It's crucial to have this level of granularity to ensure that the analyses over advanced digital skills give clear guidelines, showing the evolution of their areas of application. The same skill pocket can have an increasing trend in one technological area and at the same time demonstrate a decreasing trend in another area.

It's important to track the evolution of the ADS demand and supply over time with this level of detail.

3.1.3 Skills pockets

LEADSx2030 built on the concept of skills pockets introduced by LEADS⁵, but advanced them into *semantically* derived groupings of skills that serve as the fundamental analytical unit of the ADS Data Model. They enable consistent and comparable analysis of skill-related data across diverse domains and when the skills themselves are described in varied and unstructured ways across different data sources.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/8384358>

Each skills pocket represents a coherent cluster of related skills, identified through semantic analysis and contextual co-occurrence. This structure allows the model to reconcile linguistic variation and terminological inconsistency, ensuring that insights remain comparable across datasets.

The generation of skills pockets is based on a graph-based representation of skills:

- Skills extracted from unstructured text (e.g. job ads, training descriptions, publications) are modelled as nodes.
- Semantic relationships between skills—based on similarity, co-occurrence, and contextual alignment—are encoded as edges between nodes.
- Clusters within the graph are algorithmically identified and grouped into pockets.

Each skills pocket is anchored by a central skill, which serves as the semantic core of the cluster and summarises its dominant theme. The pocket structure is versioned, dynamic, and data-driven, continuously refined as new information becomes available and contextual factors evolve.

The process of generating and maintaining skills pockets is largely automated, leveraging Headai's language analytics infrastructure. This approach reduces the need for manual classification while preserving flexibility to adapt to emerging domains and terminologies.

Candidate pockets are evaluated based on three key criteria:

1. Relevance in the economic sector – Skills are assessed using data from job advertisements, investment trends, and sectoral reports to determine their current and anticipated significance.
2. Semantic relationship with technology areas – Skills are mapped to broader technological themes to understand how they align with developments in fields such as AI, cybersecurity, and cloud infrastructure.
3. Hierarchical position in skill structure – Skills are analysed in relation to their roles within broader clusters to determine whether they function as core competencies or as supporting elements.

Figure 1 Skills pockets formation

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	
1	process_control	system_design	process_automation	data_analytics	systems_design	automation_controls	engineering_drawings	quality_assurance	risk_control	technical_drawing	control_engineering
2	microsoft_office	business_software	management_systems	microsoft_office_word	business_systems	information_technology	system_application	microsoft_software	operating_systems	it_systems	control_engineering
3	process_automation	process_automation	management_systems	process_control	business_systems	information_technology	system_application	automation_technology	industry_automation	process_engineer	continuous_integration
4	technology_solutions	cloud_technologies	cloud_technologies	information_systems	data_as_a_service	information_technology	network_services	business_technologies	systems_technology	machine_learning	system_solutions
5	network_security	network_security	network_infrastructure	data_security	data_security	infrastructure_security	infrastructure_security	security_system	network_architecture	network_management	network_management
6	tool_management	knowledge_management	knowledge_management	information_systems	data_management	data_management	data_management	business_analytics	service_management	software_development	software_development
7	business_analytics	business_analytics	data_analytics	data_analytics	data_analytics	business_analytics	data_science	business_analytics	data_warehouse	experience_design	experience_design
8	machine_learning	machine_learning	artificial_intelligence	software_development	software_systems	it_systems	system_knowledge	computer_science	deep_learning	computer_science	data_science
9	operating_systems	software_engineering	software_development	software_systems	data_analytics	it_systems	system_knowledge	computer_science	network_security	infrastructure	computer_engineering
10	technology_operations	technology_operations	technology_operations	information_management	information_management	server_management	business_technologies	ana_management	systems_technology	service_integration_and_management	tool_management
11	sql_server	data_storage_and_integration	ci_cd	software_development	software_development	microsoft_servers	rest_api	web_services	relational_databases	cloud_infrastructure	oracle_sql
12	software_solutions	software_engineering	ci_cd	machine_learning	data_engineer	software_engineer	experience_api	experience_api	cloud_infrastructure	technology_solutions	machine_learning_algorithms
13	software_development	software_engineering	ci_cd	computer_science	data_engineer	software_engineering	application_development	systems_development	data_as_a_service	software_systems	computer_engineering
14	system_engineer	software_engineering	systems_integration	cloud_infrastructure	cloud_infrastructure	systems_design	information_systems	it_systems	integration_platform	cloud_technologies	system_development
15	user_experience	user_experience	experience_design	saas_interface	platform_as_a_service	systems_design	system_design	quality_assurance	data_quality	systems_development	ui_design
16	performance_management	data_management	data_management	local_media	management_systems	tool_management	digital_media	data_management	marketing_strategies	it_systems	key_management
17	data_as_a_service	data_management	platform_as_a_service	data_analytics	data_analytics	data_management	data_analytics	data_analytics	machine_learning	data_integration	data_processing
18	web_services	api_and_integration_services	software_development	software_development	cloud_services	cloud_services	experience_api	data_integration	web_applications	api_services	data_integration
19	computer_software	software_engineering	computer_science	information_systems	information_technology	information_technology	system_knowledge	computer_engineering	software_engineering	software_systems	data_science
20	business_systems	business_software	information_systems	systems_design	information_technology	management_systems	it_systems	data_systems	system_integration	system_integration	system_application
21	quality_assurance	quality_assurance	software_quality	software_development	data_quality	test_automation	software_testing	software_testing	systems_design	systems_design	quality_improvement
22	digital_transformation	digital_architectures	digital_data	it_transformation	digital_transformation	digital_consulting	digital_transformation_management	transformation_projects	data_management	it_consulting	digital_strategy
23	performance_monitoring	data_systems	data_systems	cloud_infrastructure	cloud_infrastructure	data_as_a_service	data_as_a_service	data_integration	system_integration	cloud_migration	cloud_migration
24	automation_engineer	devis	system_engineer	tool_engineer	tool_engineer	design_engineer	design_engineer	software_systems	process_automation	process_automation	agricultural_engineer
25	sap_knowledge	saas/rp	system_application	system_knowledge	saas/rp	saas/rp	business_technologies	saas/rp	saas/rp	saas/rp	saas/rp
26	renewable_energy	renewable_energy_technologies	energy_technology	infrastructure_as_a_service	infrastructure_as_a_service	power_engineering	power_and_energy	renewable_energy_technologies	renewable_energy_technologies	renewable_energy_systems	data_centers
27	service_support	cloud_technologies	infrastructure_as_a_service	infrastructure_as_a_service	server_engineering	server_engineering	information_technology	it_support	application_services	application_services	it_management
28	data_analytics	data_analytics	data_management	data_management	data_system	software_development	cloud_infrastructure	machine_learning	data_as_a_service	data_analytics	data_modeling
29	integration_platform	systems_integration	systems_integration	data_integration	data_integration	cloud_technologies	cloud_technologies	platform_as_a_service	technology_integration	technology_integration	business_technologies
30	system_application	system_application	it_systems	it_systems	system_integration	software_systems	information_systems	management_systems	systems_architecture	application_supports	data_system
31	python_programming_language	programming	programming_language	machine_learning	java_programming_language	programming_skills	data_analytics	software_development	c_plus_plus_programming_language	java_programming	c_plus_plus_programming
32	system_knowledge	knowledge_management	system_application	management_systems	information_systems	knowledge_management	knowledge_management	software_systems	system_design	system_design	management_development
33	it_management	knowledge_management	service_management	knowledge_management	tool_management	it_application	it_application	it_application	it_consulting	service_support	management_systems
34	infrastructure_as_a_service	cloud_technologies	data_as_a_service	cloud_services	platform_as_a_service	cloud_infrastructure	it_infrastructure	infrastructure_security	software_development	service_support	information_technology
35	information_security	business_technologies	information_systems	information_technology	security_systems	security_management	data_protection	cyber_security	cyber_security	data_security	identity_and_access_management
36	business_technologies	business_technologies	information_technology	information_technology	computer_science	information_technology	technology_solutions	computer_engineering	business_systems	business_analytics	business_transformation
37	development_engineer	software_engineering	software_development	software_development	software_engineer	system_engineer	backend_development	database_design	process_engineering	information_systems	database_development
38	programming_language	data_management	it_systems	data_management	data_analytics	python_programming_language	python_programming_language	scripting_language	scripting_language	data_visualization	business_intelligence
39	product_engineering	data_engineering	engineering_management	data_engineering	data_engineering	system_engineering	technical_engineering	production_engineering	experience_design	experience_design	manufacturing_engineering
40	cloud_architecture	software_development	software_development	experience_design	computer_science	experience_api	enterprise_architecture	cloud_technologies	business_architecture	software_architecture	programming_language
41	management_systems	knowledge_management	information_management	information_management	information_systems	software_systems	data_systems	information_management	data_management	data_management	system_application
42	regulatory_compliance	data_security	software_development	software_development	compliance_pak	cloud_security	data_protection	data_protection	data_protection	data_protection	cloud_infrastructure
43	configuration_management	cloud_infrastructure	information_management	infrastructure_management	cloud_services	information_systems	knowledge_management	tool_management	cloud_management	cloud_management	infrastructure_as_code
44	it_infrastructure	cloud_infrastructure	cloud_infrastructure	infrastructure_as_a_service	infrastructure_security	it_systems	software_development	network_infrastructure	platform_as_a_service	network_services	infrastructure_management
45	security_architecture	information_security	information_security	information_security	it_systems	system_architecture	security_system	solution_architecture	application_architecture	it_applications	it_systems
46	test_automation	test_automation	ci_cd	test_tools	software_testing	software_development	software_systems	integration_testing	quality_assurance	automation_framework	test_software

3.1.4 AI analysis methods

The Data Model employs several AI-based techniques:

- Natural Language Processing (NLP) to process unstructured text and identify skill expressions in varied contexts.
- Skill graph modelling, in which skills are represented as interconnected nodes within a graph structure. This model tracks relationships between skills and allows for comparisons and trend analysis.
- Skills clustering through semantic proximity, based on real world data co-occurrence, creating "skills pockets" that serve as the analytical unit.
- Digital twin generation, where skill profiles of job roles, curricula, or datasets are modelled and compared.

The model includes mechanisms to detect change over time. Skills pockets may evolve—splitting or merging—as new data becomes available. To support reliability, each iteration is reviewed and validated.

3.2 Data Sources

The ADS Data Model stems from its integration of a wide array of diverse data sources. This integration is central to the "data iceberg" concept, where different layers of data are combined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the digital skills landscape. The Data Hub mentioned before directly facilitates access to these varied data sources, particularly from ADS partners, enabling a comprehensive approach to skills intelligence.

Figure 2 Data ice-berg concept visualisation

1.1.1 Open data and publicly available data

Headai leverages extensive open and publicly available data sources for comprehensive analysis, representing the "tip of the iceberg." This data represents the baseline for all the studies. With this baseline we can build a strong starting point for foresight: we get big data sets without confidentiality risk, which of course requires careful curation of the valid data sources. In the Data Hub, next sections, the use of non-public non-confidential data and sensitive non-public data are described in more detail. These non-public data sets are used to bring more details and previously unknown insights into analysis.

Figure 3 Data Hub data sources visualised

The 2025 dashboard builds on a curated dataset combining several key data streams:

- EU-wide job advertisements from major platforms (see Annex II) such as EURES, Duunitori (FI), France Travail (FR), and Talent.com, yielding a total of over 3 million unique job ads in 2024, of which 210,000 explicitly reference ADS.
- Scientific publications sourced from DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)⁶, encompassing over 10 million open-access articles.
- European investment datasets, drawn from platforms such as Horizon Europe, Eureka, and selected national innovation funding databases, comprising over 100,000 investment records.^{7, 8, 9}

Description of the sample

⁶ <https://doaj.org/>

⁷ <https://data.europa.eu/en>

⁸ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

The 2024 sample of +3 million job ads offers substantial geographical coverage across the EU, representing a broad spectrum of industries, roles, and company sizes. From this sample:

- 210,000 job ads explicitly demanded advanced digital skills (ADS).
- The ADS-specific subset of 10,000 job ads was used for deep qualitative and quantitative modelling of skills trends, enabling scenario building and recommendation models.

These samples reflect a diverse occupational range, from cybersecurity experts and AI developers to digital manufacturing roles and emerging sustainability tech positions.

Scaling to the EU level

To estimate the EU-wide demand for ADS, we extrapolate from our representative sample using established statistical ratios. Based on Eurostat's JVR statistics¹⁰¹¹ and Cedefop's data dashboard¹² figures, there were between 5-8 million open jobs in the EU in 2024. Our Headai sample covered 3 millions of these jobs, constituting roughly half of the total market. In our dashboard, we took the lower end, 5 million, as a baseline. All the dashboard numbers are scaled to match this EU level baseline.

However, Job Vacancy rate (JVR) is not only indicator for open positions. It represents a snapshot of a specific time interval. Other relevant indicators are Job Vacancy Stream, which is a cumulative number of open positions in an interval, for example a year. Naturally, Job Vacancy Stream numbers are totally different to JVR: for example, in Finland JVR is typically between 50 000-60 000, while yearly Job Vacancy Stream is approximately 500 000. The third widely used indicator is Job Vacancy Stack, that estimates long-term unfilled open positions. In our current dashboard, we did not scale the numbers to Job Vacancy Stream nor Job Vacancy Stack, we only used Job Vacancy Rate.

1.1.2 Non-confidential non-public data accessed via Data Spaces

This category includes data that, while not sensitive, benefits from structured access and governance:

- Metadata from various training providers and program listings.
- Datasets contributed by other SO4 projects operating under open licensing agreements. It is recommended to apply Authorisation and Authentication mechanisms even for non-sensitive data to prevent potential Denial of Service attacks.

The data is collected / donated via LEADSx2030 Data Hub.

1.1.3 Confidential data accessed via Data Spaces

Prometheus-X¹³ skills data space has several mechanisms to ensure that the data and service offerings publicly listed in the catalogue are secure and only consumable under the specifications defined in the contract between the partners.

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-euro-indicators/w/3-18032025-bp>

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Job_vacancy_statistics

¹² <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/skills-forecast>

¹³ <https://dataspace.prometheus-x.org/>

- Shared under Gaia-X-based contracts.¹⁴
- Access governed via authentication/authorisation protocols.
- Endpoints validated using credential tokens and secure APIs.

The data is collected / donated via LEADSx2030 Data Hub.

3.3 Data Hub for external data integration

LEADSx2030 Data Hub serves as the planned integration model for expanding the ADS Data Model's data ecosystem, following a data space approach. While still under development this infrastructure is intended to enable access to a growing range of structured and unstructured data sources through standardised, secure, and governed interfaces. The Data Hub will progressively allow external data providers to contribute their datasets into the model pipeline, ensuring continuous enrichment and long-term sustainability of the model.

The Data Hub is a centralised Data Space and AI-powered infrastructure designed to support the integration, sharing, and analysis of data on ADS across sectors. It plays a key role in delivering real-time skills intelligence, forecasting capabilities, and alignment across policy, education, and industry.

Business rationale

Despite the growing importance of advanced digital skills, the data landscape remains fragmented:

- Lack of unified data sources: There is no single comprehensive resource for ADS workforce intelligence.
- Low incentives for data sharing: Industry actors often lack clear value propositions for contributing their internal workforce data.
- Regulatory challenges: Data use must align with European data frameworks such as GDPR¹⁵, Prometheus-X and the Data Space for Skills (DS4Skills)¹⁶.
- Policy-driven workforce planning: Strategic initiatives require robust data to inform funding allocation, skills gap monitoring, and training programme design.

The LEADSx2030 Data Hub aims to:

- Develop a secure and scalable architecture for data sharing.
- Establish a governance model that supports cross-sector participation and accountability.
- Enable big data pipelines that feed AI-based workforce analytics.
- Ensure full compliance with EU data regulation and open data commitments.
- Operates under the Prometheus-X governance model (Gaia-X compatible) for trusted data collaboration.

Value proposition for industry partners

The Data Hub creates a shared infrastructure with clear benefits for participating industry actors:

¹⁴ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.skillsdataspace.eu/>

- Access to tailored skills analytics and benchmark reports.
- Real-time visibility into emerging skills and workforce shifts.
- Possibility to integrate premium features such as gap analysis and future workforce planning tools.

The Leadsx2030 Data Hub is composed of four supporting layers that enable secure, AI-powered, and interoperable handling of workforce-related data:

1. Data ingestion and collaboration: Collects workforce-related data from various sources – such as job postings, education datasets like university curricula¹⁷ from ADS Cluster universities and other European universities, and industry partners (e.g. SAP, ABB) – via data space connectors and APIs. This layer supports secure data-sharing practices across stakeholders.
2. Data processing and structuring: Uses Headai's domain-specific AI models and knowledge graphs to identify skill trends, workforce gaps, and evolving job profiles.
3. Secure storage and compliance: Ensures the safe storage of sensitive and proprietary data using GDPR-compliant, encrypted, and standardised technologies.
4. Data exchange interfaces: Provides structured workforce intelligence to industry and public actors through APIs and links to broader initiatives like EU data spaces.

While this architecture underpins the project's technical infrastructure, its function in this deliverable is contextual, serving to support the design and operation of the ADS Data Model, which remains the central focus of the market data analysis.

Moving forward, the Data Hub will serve as a connector for expanding the ADS Data Model's input ecosystem. By establishing structured interfaces and governance for external data contributions, the Hub enables new data sources to be linked with the model, supporting continuous enrichment, broader representativeness, and enhanced predictive capacity.

3.4 Quality management

Different quality control processes are embedded throughout the model development:

- Human review, including feedback from stakeholders, experts and from events.
- Anomaly detection: Algorithmic identification of outliers in clustering or classification.
- NLP performance benchmarks: Use of F1-score thresholds (>0.85) for language model accuracy.
- Ontology alignment checks: Coverage analysis against ESCO¹⁸ and other similar reference systems.
- Partner validation: Ongoing feedback loops with LEADSx2030 partners on usability and analytical robustness.

The model is not only auditable but explainable, supporting its use in high-trust environments such as education policy and strategic funding allocation.

¹⁷ <https://opinto-opas.metropolia.fi/?lang=en>

¹⁸ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

4 Forecasting

The forecasting functionality embedded in the ADS Data Model represents a core feature of our activities, enabling predictive analytics for ADS across Europe. This capability is designed to address a key objective of the LEADSx2030 project: improving the strategic foresight capacity of education systems, workforce planners, and policy makers.

The forecasting layer builds upon the foundational clustering and structuring of skills (as detailed in section 3) and extends this analysis with forward-looking indicators derived from a combination of real-time labour market demand, investment trends, and research output. The methodology integrates historical time series from job advertisements (2021–2025) with future-facing signals collected from scientific publications, funding data, and innovation sources to project demand for skill pockets through 2030.

This approach enables the model to move beyond static skill taxonomies or reactive skills audits. Instead, it supports dynamic tracking of changes in digital skills demand and provides evidence for proactive decision-making across sectors and geographies.

4.1 Skills demand signals

Headai has parsed and processed millions of digital skills signals from job advertisements, sector-specific reports, investment data, and scientific literature. The resulting indicators form a statistically significant foundation for tracking demand evolution across technologies and sectors. The data is collected from years 2021-2025 and different data sets represent different time horizons: while job ads tell what is demanded in the publishing date, investment targets 2-3 years ahead of publishing date and research becomes reality somewhere between 3-10 years after the publication date. All this enables building time series for different time horizons.

Demand analysis is based on three integrated layers of data:

- Job Market Demand – Skills actively required in current labour markets.
- Investment Phase Signals – Skills identified in contexts of new funding, innovations
- Research & Innovation – Signals from academic publications highlighting future-oriented skills.

Forecast outputs can indicate growing or declining demand for particular skills pockets, and the aim is to integrate these signals into future dashboard iterations and policy briefings.

By linking historical patterns with early signals from innovation, the model provides a foundation for foresight at both policy and training design levels. Forecasting supports proactive rather than reactive planning and helps ensure strategic alignment between education, policy, and labour markets. The ADS Data Model is designed not only to structure and cluster digital skills but also to track changes in demand, reveal supply gaps, and anticipate future needs across Europe's evolving digital economy.

Outputs are presented as skill pocket demand curves, which allow tracing how clusters of skills grow, stabilise, or decline within each technology domain.

Figure 4. Example of data visualisation in Data dashboard

4.2 Skills supply signals

The supply-side analysis within the ADS Data Model framework focuses on evaluating the coverage, relevance, and timeliness of training provision in relation to emerging and established digital skill demands. The analysis aims to identify structural gaps in the current education and training ecosystem, providing evidence for curriculum reform and strategic funding decisions.

At this early stage, the supply-side mapping is based on a preliminary dataset collected directly from the SO4 ADS Cluster projects, as part of our longitudinal analysis. This dataset includes metadata on training programmes, courses and initiatives offered under the SO4 Cluster, compiled and structured by Trinity College Dublin, based on a pre-defined framework.¹⁹

As of this deliverable, the supply-side modelling remains **preliminary** and indicative, based solely on the input from the longitudinal analysis. However, this aspect of the ADS Data Model will become an analytical focus in the coming project phases, as additional datasets are integrated via the Data Hub. Future iterations will expand the scope and accuracy of supply-demand matching and support the development of more granular curriculum impact assessments and investment gap analysis tools.

4.3 Skills gap identification

One of the long-term objectives of the ADS Data Model is to enable robust gap analysis by overlaying structured supply and demand signals within each defined skill pocket. This functionality is not yet operational at the time of this deliverable

Gap identification is intended to serve as a core analytical tool for future iterations of the Data Model and for supporting policy development, training strategy design, and investment planning. The method involves aligning multiple data layers—including job market signals, training programme

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15302955>

metadata, and research outputs—to detect mismatches between what is being taught, what is being demanded, and what is emerging on the horizon.

The model is designed to classify skills gaps into three initial categories:

- Unserved pockets: Pockets with strong labour market signals but weak training provision.
- Saturated pockets: Pockets where training output exceeds demonstrated demand.
- Emerging blind spots: Skills appearing in research or innovation data but not yet present in job ads or curricula.

This multi-layered framework aims to enable fine-tuned interventions in funding allocation, curriculum development, and policy alignment once operational. In its final form, the gap identification capability is expected to support:

- Curriculum planning for higher education institutions, vocational training institutions and training providers.
- Strategic prioritisation for public agencies, national ministries and NGOs.
- Real-time monitoring and agile adjustment of the European advanced digital skills ecosystem.

4.4 LEADSx2030 Foresight model

The foresight model uses historical skills demand data from (2021–2025) along with investment and innovation trends (2021–2025) to forecast developments through 2027 and 2030. Early indicators from venture capital flows, strategic EU programmes, and patent landscapes form the basis for:

- Predicting acceleration in tech areas such as AI regulation, green digital jobs, and federated computing.
- Projecting future demand for underrepresented skill pockets and skills pockets that may emerge from current pockets.
- Identifying time-lagged or resource critical skill development needs requiring early investment.

These forecasts underpin strategic outputs that will inform policy briefs and the ADS State-of-Play reports produced in LEADSx2030.

5 Public Dashboard

The public dashboard is a real-time, interactive data visualisation platform designed to provide insights into ADS workforce demand, emerging skills, and sectoral trends. It will help policymakers, educators, and businesses make data-driven decisions regarding ADS development and workforce planning.

The public dashboard allows stakeholders to explore:

- Skill pocket demand over time.
- Trends within and across tech areas.
- Labour market saturation and training alignment.
- Predicted shifts in demand and emerging skills.

The dashboard is structured into six interactive visual layers:

1. Intro – Dataset scope and metadata overview.
2. Skill Flow – Sankey diagram linking tech areas and skills.
3. Pocket Demand – Demand indicators.
4. Trends and Trends Per Pocket– Time-series visualisations by skill pocket.
5. Tech Areas – Comparative ranking of sectors.
6. Pockets Detail – Deep dives into individual skills and definitions.

Figure 5. Example of data visualisation in Data dashboard (Version released 9.6.2025)²⁰

These features address the three core workforce intelligence questions:

- What ADS are stable in terms of demand, supply and growth, and which ADS are increasing or disappearing in terms of demand, supply and growth?
- How are skill pockets evolving and what more detailed skills are drivers for the change?
- What technology areas are driving demand?

The dashboard will support decision-making in education planning, workforce strategy, and EU-level policy setting.

²⁰ <https://advancedskills.eu/ads-demand-dashboard-updated/>

6 Conclusion

6.1 Evolution of Data Model

This deliverable has detailed the foundational work of the market data analysis in constructing a robust and transparent ADS Data Model to analyse and forecast the demand and supply of ADS in Europe. By leveraging open, publicly available datasets alongside non-confidential and sensitive data sources, the current model (V1) establishes a comprehensive baseline for skills intelligence across sectors and regions.

The baseline model utilises significant data volumes, including 4 million job ads (2024) and large-scale scientific and investment datasets. Through statistically validated extrapolation methods, this model provides a scalable and accurate reflection of ADS dynamics at the EU level. The results enable policymakers, educators, and industry stakeholders to access actionable insights on where skill gaps exist, what skills are emerging, and how to better align training and education efforts.

The ADS Data Model is designed as an iterative and continuously improving framework:

- **Version 1** (current) includes open and curated public datasets covering job demand, scientific publications, and investment signals, as outlined in this report.
- **Version 2** (planned for 2026) will integrate additional supply-side data collections and datasets shared via the LEADSx2030 Data Hub, strengthening the link between job demand and training provision.
- **Version 3** (planned for 2027) will further incorporate updated demand and supply-side datasets as well as additional contributions from LEADSx2030 Data Hub partners and newly onboarded DIGITAL projects.

Each model iteration will be accompanied by an evolution of key metrics, including:

- The number of training and educational projects represented in the supply data,
- The volume of job ads processed across geographies and sectors,
- The quantity and diversity of detected advanced digital skills.

This evolution supports longitudinal tracking of skill trends, evidence-based foresight, and continuous refinement of recommendations, ensuring the LEADSx2030 ecosystem remains aligned with Europe's fast-changing digital skill landscape.

6.2 Next steps toward D1.2 and D1.3 and connection to other WPs

Deliverable D1.1 establishes the operational ADS Data Model, setting the stage for crucial next steps and its seamless integration into subsequent activities within the LEADSx2030 project. The immediate next steps include the deployment of the full Data Hub and public dashboard (D1.2), scheduled for July 2025, and subsequent annual updates (D1.3 – D1.5) that will capture the longitudinal evolution of demand and supply.

The outputs of the ADS Data Model are designed to feed directly into other major activities, reinforcing its foundational role as the "core data engine" for the entire LEADSx2030 project:

- **Longitudinal Analysis:** The model's outputs will be utilised to benchmark the coverage and effectiveness of existing training programmes, providing a data-driven basis for assessing educational supply.

- Best Practice Capture: The model will assist in identifying successful approached and best practices from within the SO4 Cluster, contributing to the development of a comprehensive best practice library.
- Policy Recommendations and Reporting: The predictive modelling layer of the ADS Data Model will specifically generate data-backed policy briefs and comprehensive "State-of-Play" reports, providing evidence-based insights for strategic policy development.

ANNEX I - RESULTS PER TECH AREA AND SKILLS POCKET

Download the dynamic Excel sheet link:

https://cloud.headai.com/public/leadsx2030/leadsx2030_skills_pockets_alternative.xlsx

ANNEX II - DATA STREAMS OF EU-WIDE JOB ADS FOR THE DASHBOARD

Barona, <https://careers.barona.fi/>

CareersEON, <https://careers.eon.com/>

CIDJ, <https://www.cidj.com>

CVKeskus, <https://www.cvkeskus.ee>

CVMarket, <https://www.cvmarket.lv>

CvOnline, <https://www.cvonline.lt>

Duunitori, <https://duunitori.fi/>

EestiTootukassa, <https://www.tootukassa.ee>

Eezy, <https://eezy.fi/>

Eures, <https://europa.eu/eures/>

Hellowork, <https://www.hellowork.com>

Indeed, <https://www.indeed.com/about>

Jobbird, <https://www.jobbird.com>

Jobbörse, <https://www.jobbörse.de>

JobsBg, <https://www.jobs.bg/>

JobsOnline NL, <https://www.jobsonline.nl>

JobsOnline DE, <https://www.jobsonline.de>

JobTech, <https://arbetsformedlingen.se/>

Kuntarekry, <https://www.kuntarekry.fi>

Leforem, <https://www.leforem.be/>

Metacareers, <https://www.metacareers.com/>

Public employment FI, <https://paikat.te-palvelut.fi/>

Monster, <https://www.monster.com/>

France Travail, <https://www.francetravail.fr/>

SapoEmprego, <https://emprego.sapo.pt/>

Talent, <https://talent.com/>

Työmarkkinatori, <https://tyomarkkinatori.fi/>

Vacature, <https://nederlandvacature.nl>

Valtiolle, <https://valtiolle.fi>